

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF INSULIN BY UV-SPECTROSCOPY IN PHARMACEUTICAL PREPARATIONS

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ABSTRACT

A Simple, sensitive, specific, spectrophotometric method developed for the detection of Insulin. Insulin was analysed by spectrophotometry. The optimum condition for the analysis of the drug was established. The solvent selected for the study was 0.01N NaOH. The λ max of the Insulin in the chosen solvent was found to be 235nm. The developed method shows high sensitivity with linearity between 0.02 and 0.12IU/ml. The limit of detection and the limit of quantification were found to be 0.0056IU/ml and 0.0170IU/ml, respectively. All the calibration curves show a linear relationship between the absorbance and the concentration, and the coefficient correlation was higher than 0.9947. The regression of the curve was found to be $Y=4.5005x$. The precision of the method was found to be 93.19 ± 1.78 against the label claim of 10IU/ml. The method has been validated according to ICH guidelines and satisfactory results have been observed, which can be utilised for routine analysis.

Key words: *Insulin, Estimation, Pharmaceutical preparations.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Human Insulin is a protein corresponding to the active principle elaborated in the human pancreas that affects the metabolism of carbohydrates (particularly glucose), fat and protein. It is derived by enzymatic modification of insulin from pork pancreas to change amino acid sequence appropriately or produced by microbial synthesis via a recombinant DNA process [1]. It allows the sugar in the blood to leave the blood and enter the cell. After each food intake, the pancreas produces insulin to transform the nutrients taken into energy. In those with diabetes, the pancreas does not produce enough insulin or the insulin produced is not used by target cells (muscle, fat and liver cells). In this case, we need to provide insulin, which is vital for human body, from the outside. It should not be forgotten that insulin is a life-saving drug and a healthier life will be lived with the injection.

Insulin is the first protein sequenced by Frederick Sanger in 1955 [2]. The molecular formula of human insulin is $C_{257}H_{383}H_{65}O_{77}S_6$. Human Insulin also known as regular insulin, is a short-acting form of insulin used for the treatment of Hyperglycemia caused by Type 1 and Type 2 Diabetes [3]. Human insulin was produced by recombinant DNA technology where an attenuated Escherichia coli bacterium is used as a vector to produce A and B chains [4,5], the A-chain and the B-chain linked by two disulfide bonds. The molecular weight of insulin is 5.8Da [6]. The A-chain is composed of 21 amino acids, while the B-chain consists of 30 residues [7,8]. By connecting these chains with cross bridges, recombinant human insulin is obtained. The biological function of insulin is the control of glucose metabolism [6]. Human insulin plays a major role in the body by regulating blood glucose homeostasis [9]. The

insulin formulation can be administered by subcutaneous, intramuscular and intravenous injection [10].

The disruption of insulin metabolic activities due to decreased amounts of insulin, autoimmune responses, insulin responses, or insulin resistance leads to diabetes mellitus [11]. Recombinant DNA technology enables the synthesis and development of human insulin analogues with different effects, but they can also be a frequent target for adulteration [12,13]. HPLC is a very powerful tool for the analysis of peptides and proteins. Analysis of insulin has traditionally been done by biological tests [10]. Insulin is estimated using the UV spectroscopic method [14], Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy [15], Difference spectroscopy [16], Infrared spectroscopy [17], Multi-spectroscopy [18], Capillary electrophoresis mass spectroscopy [19] and HPLC combined with UV detection and mass spectroscopy (MS) [4,20-26].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Instrumentation:

A single – beam spectrophotometer (Systronics 2202) was used for the detection of absorbance. Vensil and Borosil glass apparatus were used for experimental purposes.

2.2. Chemicals & Reagents:

Human mixtard Insulin (Label claim 10ml) was purchased from the nearby pharmacies. All other chemicals used were of AR grade.

3. PROCEDURE

3.1. Preparation of stock solution:

0.5ml of insulin was pipetted out and transferred into a dry and clean 100ml volumetric flask, 10ml of 0.01N NaOH was added to the above flask, mixed well and the volume was made up with 0.01N NaOH.

3.2. Determination of absorbance maxima:

An appropriate aliquot portion of 1ml of insulin from the standard stock solution was transferred to a 10ml volumetric flask. 2ml of 0.01N NaOH was added, mixed well and made up to the volume up to 10ml with 0.01N NaOH. A UV spectrum was obtained by scanning from 400nm to 200nm.

3.3. Linearity and range:

10ml of 5 different dry and clean 10ml volumetric flasks were taken. To each flask separately 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5ml of stock solution was added. About 2ml of 0.01N NaOH was added mixed well and the volume was made up with 0.01N NaOH. Absorbance was measured at 235nm using a UV Spectrophotometer. The graph between Concentration vs Absorbance was plotted. The regression coefficient and slope for the straight line which passes through the origin was calculated.

3.4. Precision:

2ml of the standard stock solution was pipetted out and transferred into a clean and dry 10ml volumetric flask. 5ml of 0.01N NaOH was added, mixed well and made up the volume with 0.01N NaOH. The absorbance at 235nm was measured. The amount of insulin present in the sample was calculated. The above procedure was repeated six times, and the absorbance was recorded and calculated.

3.5. Accuracy:

The accuracy was performed at three different levels of 50, 100 and 150%, respectively.

3.5.1. Accuracy for 50%:

0.25ml of Insulin was pipetted out from the marketed sample and transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask. Then 0.5ml of reference insulin and 50ml of 0.01N NaOH were added and mixed well into the above volumetric flask and the volume was made up with 0.01N NaOH. The resulting solution was diluted and absorbance was measured. The above procedure was repeated in triplicates.

3.5.2. Accuracy for 100%:

0.5ml of Insulin was pipetted out from the marketed sample and transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask. Then 0.5ml of stock solution and 50ml of 0.01N NaOH were added and mixed well into the above volumetric flask, and the volume was made up with 0.01N NaOH. The resulting solution was diluted, and absorbance was measured. The above procedure was repeated in triplicates.

3.5.3. Accuracy for 150%:

0.75ml of Insulin was pipetted out from the marketed sample and transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask. Then 0.5ml of stock solution and 50ml of 0.01N NaOH were added, and mixed well into the above volumetric flask, and the volume was made up with 0.01N NaOH. The resulting solution was diluted, and absorbance was measured. The above procedure was repeated in triplicates.

3.6. Limit of detection:

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value. The detection limit (DL) may be expressed as:

$$DL=3.3\sigma/S$$

Where, σ =the standard deviation of the response. S=slope of the calibration curve.

The slope 'S' may be estimated from the calibration curve of the analyte. The estimation of σ may be carried out in a variety of ways, for example. Based on the deviation of blank, based on calibration curve, recommended data.

3.7. Limit of quantitation:

The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. The quantitation

limit is a parameter of quantitative assays for low levels of compounds in sample matrices, and is used particularly for the determination of impurities or degraded products.

$$QL=10\sigma/S$$

Where, σ =the standard deviation of the response. S=slope of the calibration curve.

The slope 'S' may be estimated from the calibration curve of the analyte. The estimation of σ may be carried out in a variety of ways, for example. Based on the deviation of blank, based on calibration curve, recommended data.

3.8. Ruggedness:

Ruggedness is a measure of reproducibility of test results under normal, expected operational conditions from laboratory to laboratory and from analyst to analyst. Ruggedness is determined by the analysis of aliquots by different analysts.

3.9. Robustness:

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters and indicates its reliability during normal usage.

3.10. Stability study:

Stability study is an integral part of many analytical procedures. The tests are based on the concept that the equipment, electronics, analytical operation and samples to be analysed constitute an integral system that can be evaluated as such. A stability test parameter is to be established for a particular procedure depending on the type of procedure being validated.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Determination of absorption maximum:

Insulin produces a chromophore in sodium hydroxide solution, which is a UV-absorbing compound with specific chromophores that enable its quantification using UV spectroscopic methods. The absorbance maximum was determined by dissolving 0.125 IU/ml of insulin in 0.01N NaOH, and the solution was scanned from 400 to 200 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. It was revealed by the absorption spectrum (Figure 1) that the λ max for insulin is found to be at 235nm in 0.01N NaOH.

4.2. Linearity and range:

Linearity study was carried out, and the data was presented in Table 1. The calibration curve was presented in Figure 2. Calibration standards for insulin covering 0.02-0.12IU/ml were prepared, and serial dilutions were made with 0.01N NaOH. The absorbance of all the resulting concentrations was measured. The calibration curve between the concentration and absorbance was plotted. The regression equation was found to be $Y=3.8429x+0.057$. The correlation coefficient (R^2) of the standard curve was found to be 0.9983.

Table 1: Linearity Profile of Insulin.

S. No.	Concentration (IU/ML)	Absorbance
1	0.02	0.141
2	0.04	0.204
3	0.06	0.289
4	0.08	0.357
5	0.1	0.443
6	0.12	0.522

Figure 1: UV-Spectrum of Insulin

4.3. Precision:

Precision was carried out, and the data was presented in Table 2.

Figure 2: Calibration curve for insulin at 235nm

Table 2: Precision Data of Insulin

S. No.	Volume of the Insulin Sample (IU/ml)	Absorbance (nm)	Insulin content present (ml)	Percentage found (%)
1	20	0.186	0.0364	91.17
2	20	0.193	0.0378	94.5
3	20	0.190	0.0372	93.13
4	20	0.186	0.0364	91.17
5	20	0.195	0.0382	95.58
6	20	0.191	0.0374	93.62
			Mean±SD	93.19±1.78

The mean precision value was found to be 93.19±1.78. The value was obtained from 91.17% to 95.58%.

4.4. Recovery:

Recovery study was carried out and the data was presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Recovery Data of Insulin

S.No.	Percentage level	Volume of the sample taken (IU/ml)	Pure drug added (IU/ml)	Total drug content (IU/ml)	Absorbance (nm)	Amount found	Amount recovered	Percentage recovery	Mean ±SD
1	50	20	10	30	0.122	0.0550	0.0178	48.06	50.30±2.42
2	50	20	10	30	0.124	0.0559	0.0187	50.4	
3	50	20	10	30	0.126	0.0568	0.0196	52.91	
4	100	20	10	30	0.167	0.0753	0.0381	102.6	101.03±1.82
5	100	20	10	30	0.164	0.0740	0.0368	99.03	
6	100	20	10	30	0.166	0.0749	0.0377	101.46	
7	150	20	10	30	0.205	0.0925	0.0553	148.7	150.78±1.90
8	150	20	10	30	0.208	0.0939	0.0567	152.43	
9	150	20	10	30	0.207	0.0934	0.0562	151.21	
									100.70±0.26

4.5. LOD and LOQ:

The Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantitation (LOQ) were calculated and found to be 0.0056IU/ml and 0.0170IU/ml.

4.6. Ruggedness:

Ruggedness data are presented in Table 4 by the spectrophotometric method, which does not show any significant difference in the absorbance. Hence, the developed method is rugged.

Table 4: Ruggedness of Insulin

S. No.	Absorbance	
	Analyst-1	Analyst-2
1	0.139	0.140
2	0.137	0.138
3	0.139	0.138

4.7. Robustness:

There is no significant difference in the absorbance observed when minor changes like nanometer and strength of sodium hydroxide differ in the spectrophotometric estimation. The observed data were presented in Tables 5 and 6, respectively.

Table 5: Robustness Study (Wavelength)

S. No.	Absorbance (234nm)	Absorbance (236nm)
1	0.139	0.143
2	0.140	0.145

Table 6: Robustness Study (Strength of NaOH)

S. No.	Strength/Absorbance	
	0.05N	0.15N
1	0.105	0.141
2	0.101	0.142
3	0.107	0.140

4.8. Stability studies:

The prepared sample solution was stable for up to 15 minutes. After 15 minutes, the absorbance got decreased, which may be due to the decomposition of the insulin in the alkali medium. The observed data are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Stability of the sample solution

Wavelength	Absorbance/Time(min.)				
	0 min	15 min	30 min	60min	120 min
235nm	0.106	0.093	0.074	0.072	0.063

4.9. Validation profile:

Performing replicate analysis of the standard solutions was used to assess the proposed method's accuracy, precision, and reproducibility. The selected concentration within the calibration range was prepared in 0.01N NAOH and analysed with the relevant calibration curves to determine the intra-day and inter-day variability. The precision was also determined and LOD & LOQ was determined and the data were presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Validation Profile of Insulin

Parameters	Observation
Coefficient of co-relation (R ²)	0.9947
Linearity range (IU/ml)	0.02-0.12

Precision (%)	93.19±1.78
Accuracy (%)	100.70±0.266
LOD (IU/ml)	0.0056
LOQ(IU/ml)	0.0170

5. CONCLUSION

A validated spectrophotometric method for quantifying Insulin in pure and formulation has been developed and validated. The developed method is selective, precise, accurate and linear over the concentration range from 0.02 to 0.12IU/ml. The precision was found to be 93.19±1.78. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.0056 IU/ml and 0.0170 IU/ml respectively, with 0.01N NaOH. The percentage of insulin recovered was 100.76±0.266. The developed method is simple and suitable for the determination of Insulin in pure and pharmaceutical preparations.

REFERENCES

- [1]. United State Pharmacopeia, Asian Edition, 2008; 2: 2405.
- [2]. Sanger F, Thompson E and Kitai R. The amide groups of Insulin, *Biochemical journal*, 1955; 59(3): 509-513.
- [3]. Oleck J, Kassam S and Goldman JD. Commentary: Why was inhaled insulin a failure in the market? *Diabetes spectrum*, 2016; 29(3): 180-184.
- [4]. Moussa B, Farouk F and Azzazy H. A validated RH-HPLC method for the determination of recombinant human insulin in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form, *E-Journal of chemistry*, 2010; 7(s1): 449-457.
- [5]. Bettelheim FA and Landesberg JM. *Laboratory experiments for introduction to general, organic and biochemistry*, Cengage Learning, Boston, USA, 2012.
- [6]. Cahill R Jr. The Banting lecture, *Physiology of Insulin in man*, *Diabetes*, 1971; 20:785-799.
- [7]. Weisse M, Steiner DF and Philipson LH. *Insulin Biosynthesis, Secretion, Structure and Structure-Activity Relationships*, Endotext, 2000.
- [8]. Zhuo Fu, Gilbert ER and Liu D. Regulation of insulin synthesis and secretion and pancreatic Beta-cell dysfunction in diabetes, *Current diabetes review journal*, 2013; 9(1): 25-53.
- [9]. Hsin-Hua Yeh, Hsin-Lung Wu, Chi-Yu Lu and Su-Hwei Chen. Simultaneous determination of regular insulin and insulin aspart by capillary zone electrophoresis and application in drug formulations, *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 2010;53: 145-150.
- [10]. Stewart G. Historical review of the analytical control of insulin, *Analyst Journal*, 1974; 99(1185): 913-928.

- [11]. Kristl A, Podgornik A and Pompe M. Simultaneous separation of insulin and six therapeutic analogues on a mixed mode column: HPLC-UV method development and application, *Journal of Chromatography B*, 2021; 1171: 122557.
- [12]. Ortner K, Buchberger W and Himmelsbach M. Capillary electrokinetic chromatography of insulin related synthetic analogues, *Journal of Chromatography*, 2009; 1216(14): 2953-7.
- [13]. Lamalle C, Servais AC, Radermecker RP, Crommen J and Fillet M. Simultaneous determination of Insulin and its analogues in pharmaceutical formulations by micellar electrokinetic chromatography, *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 2015; 111: 344-50.
- [14]. Singh Jasbir and Singh Gajendra. Area under Absorbance curve vs concentration for UV-spectrophotometric analysis of insulin in different pH conditions, 2009; 8(2): 70-75.
- [15]. Dmitry Kurouski, Micro sorci, Thomas Postiglione, Georges Belfort and Igor K Lednev. Detection and structural Characterization of insulin prefibrillar oligomers using surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy, *Biotechnology progress*, 2013; 30(2): 488-95.
- [16]. Steven Strazza, Roger Hunter, Elbert Walker and Dennis W Darnall. The thermodynamics of bovine and porcine insulin and proinsulin Association determined by concentration difference spectroscopy, *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics*, 1985; 238(1): 30-42.
- [17]. Sven Delbeck and Michael Heise H. Quality Assurance of commercial insulin formulations: Novel assay using infrared spectroscopy, *Journal of diabetes science and technology*, 2021; 15(4): 865-873.
- [18]. Sahri Yanti, Wei-Jyun Chein and Dinesh Chandra Agarwal. Profiling of insulin and resveratrol interaction using multi-spectroscopy and molecular docking study, *Beni-Suef University Journal of basic and applied science*, 2022; 11(90): 1-13.
- [19]. Narmin Hamidli, Blerta Pajaziti, Melinda Andradi, Cynthia Nagy and Attila Gaspar. Determination of human insulin and six therapeutic analogues by capillary electrophoresis-mass spectroscopy, *Journal of chromatography A*, 2022; 1678: 463351.
- [20]. Legg KM, Labay LM, Aiken SS and Logan BK. Validation of fully Automated Immunoaffinity workflow for the detection and quantification of Insulin analogs by LC-MC in Postmortem Vitreous Humor. *Journal of analytical toxicology*, 2019; 43(7): 505-511.
- [21]. Yilmaz B, Kadioglu Y and Capoglu I. Determination of insulin in humans with insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus patients by HPLC with diode array detection, *Journal of chromatographic science*, 2012; 50(7): 586-590.
- [22]. Yilmaz B and Kadioglu Y. Development and validation of HPLC method for determination of human insulin in pharmaceutical preparation, *International Journal of pharmaceutical Sciences review and research*, 2010; 2(2): 40-43.
- [23]. Salem LI, Bedmer M, Medina M and Cerezo A. Insulin evaluation in pharmaceuticals: variables in RP_HPLC and method validation, *journal of liquid chromatography & related technologies*, 1993; 16(5): 1183-1194.

- [24]. Sarmiento B, Ribeiro A, Veiga F and Ferreira D. Development and validation of a rapid reversed-phase HPLC method for the determination of insulin from nanoparticles systems, *Biomedical Chromatography*, 2006; 20(9): 898-903.
- [25]. Merve Nenni. Determination of insulin in saline by RP-HPLC combined with UV, *Hacettepe University journal of the faculty of pharmacy*, 2021; 41(2): 74-81.
- [26]. Lim SC, Roberts MJ, Paech MJ, Peng L and Jones A. Stability of insulin aspart in normal saline infusion, *Journal of Pharmacy practice and research*, 2004; 34(1):11-13.